

Comparative Study of Machine Learning Techniques to Predict Diabetic Retinopathy Using WEKA Tool

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Abstract—Diabetic Retinopathy (DR) is the maximum not unusual reason of newly identified blindness every 12 months. Annual eye checking for diabetic patients are cautioned so that it will locate and treat DR in a well-timed way, thinking about that blindness from this circumstance is preventable with early detection. DR detection is purely based totally on gift affected character information. Now an afternoon's scientific information growing specially and we need to specify that information for detection. However it's time ingesting as a result records mining techniques facilitates to get rid from this issue. This paper compares the output of various machine learning techniques like Random Forest, OneR and J48 on diabetic retinopathy dataset in order to determine which algorithm is best for predicting diabetic retinopathy correctly.

Keywords—Machine Learning, Diabetic Retinopathy, Random Forest, J48, OneR, Weka, Accuracy

I. INTRODUCTION

Machine learning is a type of data analysis that automates the creation of analytical models. It's a field of artificial intelligence based on the premise that computers can learn from data, recognize patterns, and make decisions with minimal human intervention. This study aims to find best algorithm to predict the diabetes retinopathy dataset based on different features using the different techniques of Machine Learning (ML).

The variety of Diabetic patients go to pot from a medical condition within the retina of the eye called as DR. There are a couple of degrees of DR, which in order of enhancing austerly are: slight non-proliferative diabetic retinopathy (NPDR), slight

NPDR, severe NPDR, and proliferative DR. The

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principle supply of DR is excessive blood sugar stages over a long term period within the retina called Diabetes Mellitus [1]. On the premise of eye test, there are permit developments in the retina as DR progresses that assist clinicians in differentiating one stage from different. the ones consist micro-aneurysms, intra- retinal hemorrhages, retinal ischemia and finally the proliferation or increase of fragile new blood vessels that can bleed on the inner ground of retina [2].implemented approach will come across the presence or absence of retinopathy. More research is being conducted on diabetes retinopathy every day because of their health problems.

To predict diabetes retinopathy, a computer-based system is needed. Through the records evaluation techniques the huge facts set may be without problems techniques through the various algorithms. The beneficial and required pattern gets skilled and processed for predicting the correct resulted [5].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Siddharekh S. Patil¹, Kalpana Malpe¹ says that medical statistics developing tremendously and we need to procedure that information for detection. But it's a large consuming as a result records mining techniques allows to get rid from this trouble. We use neural network (NN) and naïve bayes for classification.

In line with comparison effects NN gives better accuracy than naïve bayes and time and reminiscence required for NN is less as compared to naïve bayes.

Satwik Ramchandre, Bhargav Patil, Shardul Pharande, Karan Javali, Himangi Pande says that the experimental results display that the training accuracy of this method can reach very high. As a result, the retina pix of the

Diabetic and healthful sufferers may be easily classified

the usage of our proposed method, consequently lowering the range of critiques by means of scientific experts.

Vasima Khan³, Deepshikha Patel³, Tariq Azfar Meenai³, Rajesh S³ used deep gaining knowledge of approach that detect diabetic retinopathy in patients the usage of their retina fundus images. They have performed an accuracy of seventy three% which is lots more that of preceding paintings executed.

III. METHODOLOGY

The aim of this study is to classify Diabetes retinopathy dataset into two categories (presence and absence) using machine learning techniques [1]. This phase provides the type methodology used to categorize the Diabetes retinopathy based on the distinctive capabilities[3]. The methodology includes three important stages that are gathering dataset, pre-processing and class as shown in figure 1.

A. WEKA

It is an open source software that includes tools for data pre-processing, machine learning algorithm implementation, and visualization tools, allowing you to create system getting to know techniques and follow them to real-world information mining issues[4]. WEKA implements a number of algorithms in every of these classes. You could select a set of rules and set the preferred parameters and run it on the dataset[4]. Then, WEKA might come up with the statistical output of the version processing. The diverse fashions can be applied on the equal dataset [4]. You could then examine the outputs of various fashions and pick out the nice that

meets your reason. Consequently, the use of WEKA results in a faster improvement of machine learning models at the whole[4]

Figure1: Methodology for Diabetes Retinopathy Classification

B. Collecting Dataset

A number of variables are used to classify whether a person has chance for diabetes retinopathy. The dataset used in this study comes from the Kaggle repository, and it contains 772 instances of diabetes retinopathy with 9 attributes and a known target class. This data set is used as training data for the classifier.

C. Pre-Processing

In data mining, pre-processing is a crucial stage. It deals with entries that are missing, incomplete, or invalid for an expansion of motives, which include statistics entry errors. Similarly, there also are attributes that are not relevant to the studies in facts mining [3]. Besides the point records consisting of identification have to also be removed from the dataset due to the fact its presence can reduce the nice or accuracy of the statistics mining category test [3]. The dataset for this study is made up of nominal values. These data must be turned into numerical values, this means that the nominal values should be transformed into numerical values [3]. Through reworking the nominal into numerical values, the statistics are actually capable of fed into class algorithm [3].

D. Classification Experiment

The classification test is carried out the usage of Waikato environment for knowledge analysis (WEKA). In this paper, we will use different machine learning algorithms and techniques for prediction of diabetes retinopathy such as Decision Stump, OneR, Random Forest and compare the results to see which algorithm has the best accuracy for the proper prediction of presence and absence of diabetes retinopathy in a person.

Evaluation Matrix

An evaluation matrix is necessary for evaluating the consequences of a type experiment [3]. The purpose is to create a single size that may be used throughout a couple of class techniques in order that effects can be compared [3]. In this work, the evaluation metrics used includes the

classification accuracy, coefficient metric, and time taken to build the model.

IV. IMPLIMENTATION

In this study, we will use different machine learning algorithms and techniques for diabetes retinopathy and are listed below:

A. Classification Algorithms

J48 Algorithm: It is a decision tree technique and is one the most popular classification techniques in machine learning, where it used in decision support system. It enables you to predict the target variable of a new dataset record [5].

With the aid of learning simple choice rules inferred from beyond statistics, the reason of employing a j48 is to broaden a training model that can be used to expect the magnificence or cost of the goal variable (schooling information). We begin from the root of the tree whilst the use of selection bushes to predict a class label for a file. The values of the root characteristic and the report's characteristic are in comparison.

J48 is based totally on a top-down approach, a recursive divide and conquer approach. You pick which characteristic to break up on at the basis node, and you then create a department for each possible characteristic value, and that splits the instances into subsets, one for each department that extends from the basis node.

Correctly Classified Instances	567	73.8281 %
Incorrectly Classified Instances	201	26.1719 %
Kappa statistic	0.4164	
Mean absolute error	0.3158	
Root mean squared error	0.4463	
Relative absolute error	69.4841 %	
Root relative squared error	93.6293 %	
Total Number of Instances	768	

=== Detailed Accuracy By Class ===

TP Rate	FP Rate	Precision	Recall	F-Measure	MCC	ROC Area	PRC Area	Class
0.814	0.403	0.790	0.814	0.802	0.417	0.751	0.811	tested negative
0.597	0.186	0.632	0.597	0.614	0.417	0.751	0.572	tested positive
Weighted Avg.		0.738	0.327	0.735	0.738	0.736	0.417	0.727

=== Confusion Matrix ===

a	b	<- classified as
407	93	a = tested_negative
108	160	b = tested_positive

Figure1: Classification Accuracy by J48

Random Forest: Random forest is a versatile, smooth to apply gadget gaining knowledge of set of rules that produces, even without hyper-parameter tuning, an extraordinary end result maximum of the time. It's also one of the most used algorithms, due to its simplicity and variety (it may be used for each category and regression duties).

It is a decision tree classification and regression extension of bagging. Its miles a selection tree type and regression extension of bagging. It is an ensemble of choice trees, normally trained with the "bagging" method.

The general concept of the bagging approach is that a combination of getting to know models will increase the general end result [6]. Bagged selection bushes have the drawback of being constructed the use of a greedy set of rules that selects the first- class split point at every stage of the tree-constructing manner[5].

```
Correctly Classified Instances  582    75.7813 %
Incorrectly Classified Instances  186    24.2188 %
Kappa statistic                0.4566
Mean absolute error            0.3106
Root mean squared error        0.4031
Relative absolute error        68.3405 %
Root relative squared error    84.5604 %
Total Number of Instances      768
```

=== Detailed Accuracy By Class ===

```
TP Rate FP Rate Precision Recall F-Measure MCC ROC Area PRC Area Class
0.836 0.388 0.801 0.836 0.818 0.458 0.820 0.886 tested_negative
0.612 0.164 0.667 0.612 0.638 0.458 0.820 0.679 tested_positive
Weighted Avg. 0.758 0.310 0.754 0.758 0.755 0.458 0.820 0.814
```

=== Confusion Matrix ===

```
a b <- classified as
418 82 | a = tested_negative
104 164 | b = tested_positive
```

Figure2: Classification Accuracy by Random Forest

OneR: OneR classifier is one of the most simple and successful classifier algorithms for machine learning classification issues. It creates one rule for each predictor in the data, then chooses the rule with the smallest overall error to be its single rule.

Correctly Classified Instances	549	71.4844 %
Incorrectly Classified Instances	219	28.5156 %
Kappa statistic	0.3226	
Mean absolute error	0.2852	
Root mean squared error	0.534	
Relative absolute error	62.7398 %	
Root relative squared error	112.0334 %	
Total Number of Instances	768	

=== Detailed Accuracy By Class ===

TP Rate	FP Rate	Precision	Recall	F-Measure	MCC	ROC Area	PRC Area	Class
0.866	0.567	0.740	0.866	0.798	0.334	0.649	0.728	tested_negative
0.433	0.134	0.634	0.433	0.514	0.334	0.649	0.472	tested_positive
Weighted Avg.								
0.715	0.416	0.703	0.715	0.699	0.334	0.649	0.639	

=== Confusion Matrix ===

```

a b <- classified as
433 67 | a = tested_negative
152 116 | b = tested_positive
    
```

Figure4: Classification Accuracy by OneR

V. RESULT

The classification of this dataset was done to predict the chance of presence of diabetes retinopathy or not based on their characteristics. The dataset had a total of 9 nominal attributes (features). Result of the testing using evaluation on the training dataset indicate that Random Forest has 75.7% accuracy level, J48 has 73.8% accuracy and OneR has 71.4% accuracy. However, the Random Forest method is faster than J48 and OneR in terms of processing speed. Below Table1 shows the performance comparison chart of three algorithms on Diabetic Retinopathy dataset.

ML Techniques	Accuracy	Time Taken to Build a Mode
Random Forest	75%	0.03s
J48 Algorithm	73.00%	0.02s
OneR	71.40%	0.25s

Table 1: Performance Comparison Chart

VI. CONCLUSION

Diabetes Retinopathy Prediction help in prevention and early detection. Via the predictive evaluation and early detection mechanism of various facts mining technique, the numerous epidemic sicknesses may be to begin with analyzed, recognized, controlled and avoided. This paper offered the technique and effects for Diabetes Retinopathy classification test primarily based on their behavioral capabilities.

This comparison study has given us a better understanding of how the various machine learning models work and how they perform in real-world scenario. The end result suggests that Random Forest technique holds correct for the evaluation of scientific records class mainly for Diabetes Retinopathy than J48 Algorithm and OneR

VII. FUTURE WORK

In data mining, we know that as the size of training dataset increases, the performance of the created model would be enhanced. As a future work, we can also include other attributes like partial blindness, full blindness, age etc. and more records that are collected as part of research and apply different machine learning techniques on the new dataset. This will result in improving the model accuracy of the test.

VIII. REFERENCES

- [1] Siddharekh S. Patil, Kalpana Malpe "Implementation of Diabetic Retinopathy Prediction System Using Data Mining"
- [2] Satwik Ramchandre, Bhargav Patil, Shardul Pharande, Karan Javali, Himangi Pande "A Deep Learning Approach for Diabetic Retinopathy Detection using Transfer Learning"
- [3] Vasima Khan, Deepshikha Patel, Tariq Azfar Meenai, Rajesh Shukla "Application of Deep Learning Techniques for automating the detection of diabetic retinopathy in retinal fundus Photographs"
[4]https://www.tutorialspoint.com/weka/what_is_weka.htm
- [5] N. Bhargava and G. Sharma, "Decision Tree Analysis on J48 Algorithm for Data Mining" [6]<https://builtin.com/data-science/random-forest-algorithm>.